

Heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA involving mercury and some other metal ions

G. K. Mishra, K. P. Singh and V. Krishna*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

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Equilibrium studies on heterobinuclear complexes of the ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) with $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{La}^{\text{III}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}\text{-Hg}^{\text{II}}$ have been carried out pH-metrically at 25° and at constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3). The overall stability constant ($\log \beta$) have been evaluated by using SCOGS computer program. The heterobinuclear complex species of the type MHgDTPA have been detected.

The ability of polyaminopolycarboxylic acids to form generally stable and readily soluble complexes over the entire pH range with a variety of metal ions is the reason for their extensive and diversified application. In this development ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) played a central role and stimulated interest in the higher homologues, such as diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) or triethylenetetraminehexaacetic acid (TTHA) in order to develop ligands with an increased affinity and selectivity of metal detoxication¹. Some of the DTPA complexes have been utilized as contrast enhancing agents in biomedical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)². This is the reason why the binary and ternary complexes with this ligand and its variously substituted derivatives have recently become the subject of extensive investigations in solution^{3,4} and in the solid state⁵. We report here the formation and stability of heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA involving Hg and some other metal ions (Cu, Zn, Cd, La, Pr and Nd) in aqueous solution.

Results and Discussion

The octadentate ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) forms binary complexes with Cu, Zn, Cd, Hg, La, Pr and Nd metal ions in aqueous solution. Among these complexes, HgDTPA has the highest stability and therefore it can be presumed that in a 1 : 1. M : HgDTPA reaction mixture Hg^{II} remains fully complexed and the reaction mixture mainly contains the species $[\text{HgDTPA}]$ and $[\text{M}]$ at pH lower than 2.5. This reaction condition of low pH is maintained by adding requisite amount of acid to the reaction mixture. When pH of the reaction mixture is raised by adding alkali, the dissociable protons (H^+) of the uncoordinated carboxyl groups of HgDTPA are displaced as per following equilibria :

The completely deprotonated ligand which becomes available in greater quantity with rising pH interacts with the other metal ion (M) forming the heterobimetallic complex $[\text{MHgDTPA}]$ as

The HgDTPA complex is expected to involve four-coordinate tetrahedral arrangement around Hg^{II} as this is the most preferred coordination for Hg^{II} metal ion⁶. In the species HgDTPA , the Hg^{II} is expected to bound to two amino nitrogen and two carboxylic groups in a tetrahedral fashion and it has still some vacant coordination sites available for interaction with another metal ion and thus making the formation of heterobinuclear complex $[\text{MHgDTPA}]$ possible. The heterobinuclear complexation equilibria in the pH range 2.5–5.0 are

The overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) for the above heterobinuclear complexes have been determined at the 25° by using the SCOGS computer program⁷ and are given in Table 1. The $\log \beta$ values for binary systems of all these metal ions under the present experimental conditions have been already reported by us⁴.

Table 1. Overall stability constant ($\log \beta$) values for M Hg DTPA (1 : 1 : 1) type heterobinuclear complexes in aqueous solution* $I = 0.1 M$ (NaNO₃), Temp. = 25 ± 1°

Complex species	$\log \beta$
[Cu ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	30.08
[Zn ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	26.30
[Cd ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	26.25
[La ^{III} Hg ^{II} DTPA]	26.32
[Pr ^{III} Hg ^{II} DTPA]	27.40
[Nd ^{III} Hg ^{II} DTPA]	26.12

*Limit of error : ± 0.02 in log scale.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Metal nitrate solutions were standardized by complexometric EDTA titrations.

pH was measured with a Century Cp 901S pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) at 25°. The reaction mixtures were prepared keeping the volume 50.0 ml, ionic strength 0.1 M (NaNO₃), free acid concentration 0.02 M (HNO₃), metal ion and ligand concentration 0.001 M. The ratio of M : Hg : DTPA was kept 1 : 1 : 1. All the mixtures were then separately titrated with carbonate-free 0.1 M NaOH solution⁸. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature⁹. Stability constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS computer program⁷. Preliminary estimates of constants supplied to the computer were obtained from literature¹⁰.

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